

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

Norboyeva Madina Azamat qiziAssistant, Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.**Ortiqov Nosir Tojimurodovich**Doctor of Technical Sciences (PhD),
Tashkent Research Institute of Chemical Technology,
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.nosir.ortiqov@bk.ru**Abdulahat Djalilov Turapovich,**Doctor of Chemistry, Academician,
Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Chemical Technology,
Uzbekistan, Tashkent**Karimov Mas'ud Ubaydulla O'g'li**Doctor of Technical Sciences, professor,
Tashkent Research Institute of Chemical Technology,
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.

SYNTHESIS OF A NEW SUPERPLASTICIZER FROM LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

Abstract: In this article, the reaction equations and technological processes for the synthesis of a superplasticizer based on local pyrolysis raw materials are studied. An analysis of the IR spectrum is also presented.

Keywords: Pyrolysis oil, sulfuric acid and formalin, diethanolamine, naphthalenesulfonic acid formaldehyde, naphthalene β -naphthalenesulfonic acid, plasticizer, stabilizer.

Introduction: Today, with the rapid development of the construction industry around the world, the demand for high-quality durable building materials is growing day by day. A number of scientific and practical works are being carried out in our republic, such as the development of the construction industry, the modernization of the production of building materials, the effective use of local and secondary raw materials in the production of building materials, at the same time, an increase in production [1; 6276-6285 p.,].

In recent years, the use of chemical additives to concrete mixes has been one of the most important problems in our republic, and the synthesis of new organic plasticizers that increase the durability and strength of structures suitable for climatic conditions and aggressive environments is considered one of the most important urgent problems. [2; 108.p.,].

At the same time, the use of concrete mix with chemical additives based on local raw materials leads to the construction of durable buildings and high economic efficiency. Superplasticizers are the most effective chemical additives for concrete mixtures. Chemical admixtures are an effective and easy way to improve the quality of a concrete mix [3; 99-102-b.,].

With their help, strong, frost-resistant and durable concrete structures are made.

Additives used to change the properties of concrete mixtures are divided into 3 groups:

- additives that improve the properties of ready-made concrete mixtures of the first group [4; 16–18 p.,].

These include plasticizing, stabilizing, pore-forming (macro- and micropore-forming), fluidity regulating additives.

- The second group includes additives that regulate the kinetics of hardening (acceleration, deceleration) of concrete mixtures, increase strength, reduce electrical conductivity, increase the chemical properties of steel reinforcement, and change other properties. [5; 1 p.,].

- The third group of additives gives special properties to concrete mixtures, such as frost resistance, hydrophobicity, increased salt resistance

At present, most of the plasticizers for concrete mixtures used in the construction industry of our country are imported from foreign countries. In this place, cost-effective plasticizers have been synthesized that can replace imports [6; 49-51 p.,].

EXPERIMENTAL PART:

Pyrolysis oil, 85% sulfuric acid and formalin are added to a container equipped with a stirrer and heating, the mass ratio of substances is as follows: 1:1:2.74, after which the solution is stirred at a temperature of 70°C for 60 minutes. After complete melting of the pyrolysis oil, the reaction is continued for 3 hours at 160 °C. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture is cooled and neutralized with diethanolamine. The neutralized mixture is dried at a temperature of 70 °C. At the same time, the output of naphthalenesulfo-formaldehyde products is 78.8%. In the process of obtaining a plasticizing additive based on pyrolysis oil, the ratio of the initial products is of particular importance.

In the course of the reaction, along with β-naphthalenesulfonic acid, naphthalene disulfonic acids or dinaphthylsulfones with a double naphthalene ring can also appear.

Naphthalene β - naphthalenesulfonic acid

in the second step of the reaction

The IR spectra of the obtained raw material and the synthesized product were compared.

RESULT AND ITS DISCUSSION:

Picture. 1. IR spectrum of pyrolysis oil.

With an increase in the number of aromatic rings, the number of absorption bands in the lower frequency part of the IR spectrum increases. You can see this in the IR spectra of pyrolysis oil. The line near 3051.39 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum is due to IR stretching vibrations of the C-H bond in the naphthalene molecule. The intense peak at 783.10 cm⁻¹ is due to vibrations of the naphthalene ring in a plane different from the plane of the ring. The absorption bands of the benzene ring at 1456.26 and 1506.41 cm⁻¹ turned out to be -C-C- at 738.74 cm⁻¹.

The IR spectrum of the synthesized superplasticizer after neutralization with diethanolamine was studied.

Figure

2. IR analysis of superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine

As can be seen from Figure 2, after processing the raw material by the IR spectrum, it can be said that the resulting superplasticizer mainly has the following functional groups. New absorption bands in the region of 1616.35 cm⁻¹ indicate that the functional group -COO- has changed its structure to the chemical bond R-SO₂-R. The IR spectrum contains absorption lines of asymmetric stretching vibrations in the region of -1082.06 cm⁻¹ and characteristic absorption lines of symmetric stretching vibrations in the region of 756.10-667.37 cm⁻¹. This indicates that the synthesized superplasticizer has a functional group. It can be seen from the obtained results that the formation of the synthesized superplasticizers is reflected in the IR spectra.

The thermogravimetric analysis curve of the superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine is studied and the analyzes are presented. The thermal analysis analysis of the superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine is presented in Figure 3 and consists of two lines. Analysis of the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curve (curve 1) shows that the mass loss on the TGA curve mainly occurs in the 1st temperature range.

Figure 3. DTA analysis of superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine

Table 1
Tabular presentation of TGA analysis of superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine

Diethanolamine	Mass loss, g	Mass loss, %
34-187 ⁰ C	-0.280	-4.607
187-514.64 ⁰ C	-2.884	-47.450
514.64-901.68 ⁰ C	-0.494	-8.128
Overall	-3.658	-60.185

Table 2
Tablichnyy vid analiza DTA superplasticatora, neytralizatsiyalangan dietanoaminom

Diethanolamine	Total energy absorption, μV	Unit of measurement relative to mass, $\mu\text{V}/\text{mg}$	Теплый	Heat to Ground
263.92°C	2.31		-140.07	

Thermal analysis of the newly synthesized superplasticizer (naphthalenesulfonic acid formaldehyde) was studied in the frequency range of 20–950°C. The derivatogram is shown in the figure. 2 and consists of 2 curves. On the derivatogram of the resulting plasticizer, five endothermic effects were observed at temperatures of 50.23, 94.03, 138.71, 750.16, 782.49°C. In the temperature range of 20-300°C, the mass of the substance decreases by 14.812% (-1.041 mg). Endoeffects 1 and 2 indicate the evaporation of hygroscopic water from the plasticizer, and endoeffect 3 corresponds to the temperature of the liquefaction of the plasticizer. The weight loss in the temperature range of 300-600°C was 9.050% (-0.636 mg). No peaks were observed on the DTA curve in this temperature range. In the temperature range 600-950°C, the weight loss was 39.172% (-2.753 mg). In this temperature range, two endothermic peaks were observed on the DTA curve at 750.16 0C and 782.49 °C. The endothermic peak observed at 750-160°C represents the breakdown of bonds in the plasticizer. When DTA analysis of the obtained superplasticizer was observed 1 endothermic effect in the temperature range of 20-950°C.

The results of SEM analysis of the superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine were studied

Display name	Standard data	Quantification method	Result Type
Spc_001	Standardless	ZAF	Metal

Element	Line	Mass%	Atom%
C	K	52.44±0.31	61.99±0.37
N	K	6.79±0.31	6.88±0.32
O	K	29.41±0.40	26.10±0.35
S	K	11.35±0.11	5.03±0.05
Total		100.00	100.00
Spc_001			Fitting ratio 0.0288

Rice. 4. Results of elemental analysis and analysis of the superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine.

On the SEM image of the superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine in Fig. 4, it was found that the mass fraction of the functional group in the composition of the elements is 52.44% carbon, 29.41% oxygen, 6.79% metallic sodium and 11.35% gold sulfur.

Table 3

Physical and chemical parameters of the superplasticizer neutralized with diethanolamine

Name of indicators	In the form of a solution	In powder form
	Significance of indicators for additions	
Appearance	Homogeneous dark brown liquid	The same light brown powder
Density at 20°C, g/sm ³	1,07	0,5
Mass fraction of water, no more than %	70	3,0
Hydrogen ion activity indicator (pH), 2.5% aqueous solution	7,0	7,0
Mass fraction of chlorine ions in dry matter, not more than	2,0	2,0
Solubility in water 20 0C, g/100 g of water	-	50

Table 3 shows that the resulting plasticizer meets almost all the requirements of GOST for additional technical parameters. The synthesis of such superplasticizers is one of the urgent problems. The resulting superplasticizers serve as a practical solution to these current problems.

References

1. Гульмат Д., Вахидулла Х. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ВЫСОКОПРОЧНЫХ БЕТОНОВ В КОНСТРУКЦИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ВЫСОТНЫХ ЗДАНИЙ //StudNet. 2022. Т. 5. №. 6. С. 6276-6285.
2. Ломаченко Д. В. ВЛИЯНИЕ СУПЕРПЛАСТИФИКАТОРА СБ-3 НА РЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ СВОЙСТВА ЦЕМЕНТНЫХ СУСПЕНЗИЙ //Современные наукоемкие технологии. 2004. №. 2. С. 108.
3. Вишневский В.И. Супер и гиперпластификаторы для бетонов нового поколения //В.И. Вишневский, Е.А. Шкред Текст: непосредственный, электронный //Технические науки в России и за рубежом: материалы VIIМеждунар. Науч. Конф. (Москва, ноябрь 2017 г.) Москва: Буки-Веди, 2017 г. 99-102 с.
- 4.Тарасов В. Н. Отечественные поликарбоксилатныесуперпластификаторы производства ООО «НПП «Макромер» для бетона, гипса и строительных смесей /В. Н. Тарасов //Технологии бетонов, 2015. № 12. 16–18 с.
- 5.Современные суперпластификаторы для сухих строительных смесей: [Электрон, ресурс]: Информ. бюллетень журн. Строительство. Новосибирск, 2006. Режим доступа: WWW. URL: [HTTP://www. TROTUAR.RU](http://www.TROTUAR.RU) 14.10.2006. 1с

6. Гувалов А. А., Аббасова С. И., Кузнецова Т. В. Эффективность модификаторов в регулировании свойств бетонных смесей //Строительные материалы. – 2017. – №. 7. – С. 49-51.

